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The study on the relationships among organizational culture, strategies of the TVE Reform Project and competitive advantage of TVE Institutions in Taiwan

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ABSTRACT

The main purpose of the paper is to investigate the relationships among organizational culture, strategies of Phase II of the Technological and Vocational Education (TVE) Reform Project and competitive advantage of TVE Institutions in Taiwan. In order to achieve the objectives, the subjects of this paper were TVE Institutions that carried out the TVE Reform Project for phase II. Research methods of this paper included literary analysis, focus group interview, and questionnaire survey. The information obtained by the questionnaires had been analyzed by Hierarchical Linear Modeling (HLM). The results were discussed to analyze the relationship between strategies of Phase II of the TVE Reform Project and

competitive advantage of TVE Institutions. Furthermore, the moderating effect of organizational culture was tested.

The paper constructed the relationships among organizational culture, strategies of Phase II of the TVE Reform Project and competitive advantage of TVE Institutions for hierarchical linear model. The positive influences between variables of strategies of Phase II of the TVE Reform Project and competitive advantage were supported. The positive influences between variables of organizational culture and competitive advantage were supported, too. However, the moderating effect of organizational culture was not supported. Finally, according to the results of empirical study, the suggestions for strategies of the technological and vocational education and future research were proposed.

Conference Key Areas : Curriculum Development, Ethics and Engineering Education, Quality Assurance and Accreditation

Keywords : Phase II of the TVE Reform Project, organizational culture, competitive advantage, Hierarchical linear modeling (HLM)

1 INTRODUCTION

The paper investigated the relationships among organizational culture, strategies of Phase II of the Technological and Vocational Education (TVE) Reform Project and competitive advantage of TVE Institutions in Taiwan. This chapter is divided into three sections, hereby issues statement on the research background and motivation, purpose and scope of the study and restrictions, are described as follows.

1.1 Research Description

In Taiwan, human Resource has been the proud competitive advantage in recent years. However, the school-age population will continue decrease, which affecting the use of educational resources at all levels and affect the future quality and quantity of human resources . By globalization, international politics, knowledge-based economy of environmental constraints, industry changes in industrial structure and production styles towards high-tech development, so internationalization and localization had attracted attention from industry-oriented technical and vocational universities.

School-based management has become a new force and new trends. Schools have been established to shape the characteristics of the school organizational culture. The school management will need to integrate education resources and meet new competition. Therefore, when environment changes, marketing strategy has become one of the important tasks for leaders, the study of the industry demand-oriented technology reform project, technical and organizational college organizational culture and competitive advantage are a very important issue in Taiwan.

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1.2 Research Background

Relationship between technical and vocational education and economic development in Taiwan is extremely tight. Education is an important basis for capital construction and economic development, and personnel training has been the most important national assets in the knowledge economy tide. Industry demand for specialized functions and management personnel is more demanded. Technical and vocational schools should play an important role to teach expertise skills. Therefore, to study the competitive advantages for vocational schools is necessary and is the researching motivations of the paper.

1.3 Purpose of Study

Based on the above research background and motivation of this study, to explore the industrial demand-driven technical and vocational reform project, research on organizations and cultures of vocational colleges and their competitive advantage may provide the value of reference of policy assessment and policy execution. Based on the above context, the present study has the following main purposes: First, discuss strategy and status of vocational colleges and cultural organizations and competitive advantages of the recycling program of technical and vocational school. Second, analyze the influence of strategies of the TVE Reform Project on competitive advantages. Third, analyze the influence of organizational culture on competitive advantage. Fourth, analyze the moderating effects of the technical and vocational colleges' organizational culture between strategies of TVE Reform Project and the competitive advantage.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Technical and Vocational Education Reform Project

The phase II of technical and vocational education reform project is mainly combined with industry, government, academia and research resources in Taiwan. The project cultivated the required technical human resources at all levels according to the Industry and business demands and enhanced the overall competitiveness of technical and vocational education. Below are the objectives:

1. Students will possess job-required expertise.
2. Provide the high quality technical manpower to the industries.
3. Change social views on technical and vocational education.

The phase II of technical and vocational education reform project includes the following three dimensions: system adjustment, activation programs, and employment promotion (Ministry of Education, 2013) [1].

2.2 Organizational Culture

For organizational culture, Lapiņa, Kairiša, and Aramina believe that organizational performance is directly related to the organizational culture and organizational effectiveness [2]. Arabaci believes that the existing education management and leadership theory ignores the importance of values and culture. Culture is a combination of the intelligence structures by beliefs, values and actions. Cultural Gives meaning of life. The values of school administrator are the source of intent [3]

The nature of vocational college's organizational culture is different from the normal universities. Positioning, functional organization, cultural structure, organizational competition, and general operating methods are all different from traditional organizations. Kathleen also mentioned that students were affected by organizational

culture such as principal's behaviors from analyzing 81 research reports [4]. In addition, teachers are one of the main members of the school organization, so the main policy should focus on the professional competence of teachers.

2.3 Competitive Advantage

Competitive advantage in the school section, Prahalad and Hamel believe that the concept of core competencies of the organization can integrate the advantages of resources, thereby establishing a long-term competitive advantage [5]. Lynch and Baines emphasized the school's competitive advantage not only related to these competing resources and contents, and is also closely related with the development of resources (Mazzarol and Soutar, 1999) [6].

Lynch and Baines believes that if schools want to enhance their competitiveness to gain advantage, school leaders must first evaluate the schools themselves from all perspectives; it must construct schools as learning organizations, quality of leadership, and flexible administrative system in order to diversified management style. For identification of the university's competing resource, the reputation of the structure, innovation, core competencies, and knowledge advantage are significant factors [7].

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Structure and Sampling

The paper focuses on the relationship among the TVE reform project, organization culture, and competition advantage of schools. The research designs the TVE reform project as independent variable, organization culture as mediator, and competition advantage as dependent variable. The sampling methods are summarized as the following: first, the population: teachers from vocational and technical high schools and universities. Second, the samples: the research applies purposive sampling to select even numbers of teachers from each of north, central, and southern Taiwan.

3.2 Research Implementation

The samples are selected according to their geographic locations. A total of 34 schools are selected in this research, and 1,196 surveys are returned, with valid surveys of 1,183; the valid rate is 98.9%. The school-level(organizational level) and personal(individual-level) samples collected in this study. The collected data are aggregated as organizational level from individual-level so the research is analyzed by hierarchical linear models (referred to as HLM).

3.3 Data Processing Method

After the surveys were collected and coded, the data is analyzed by HLM to process information. In this study, the statistical significance is $\alpha = 0.05$. In this study, statistical analysis HLM verifies the hypothesis proposed in this study to explore the relationship among the strategies of the TVE reform project, organization culture, and competition advantage of schools.

4 RESEARCH ANALYSIS

A hierarchical linear model is used to analyze the data, and according to null model, random coefficient regression model, intercept model and full model, the test to the statistical results indicate significant influence among the variables. Before hierarchical linear model analysis, the research needs to examine each of the variables – independent, dependent, and mediator – reach the within-group

agreement of σ^2 and the between-group variation, of τ_{00} . According to the research framework of this study, technical and vocational schools belong to the organizational level of each vocational school are directly responded from the teachers of each school in order to satisfy the within-group agreement and between-group variation.

4.1 Null Model

In this study, null model verifies the effect of different schools of competitive advantage, correlation coefficients, and the overall reliability. When the competitive advantage among schools are significantly different, detailed HLM analysis is required for further research.

Random Effect	Standard Deviation	Variance Component	<i>d.f.</i>	χ^2	<i>p</i> -value
INTRCPT1, u_0	0.21791	0.04748	33	240.53438	<0.001
level-1, r	0.50641	0.25645			

Random effect is the variation of the number $r_{ij} = 0.256$, $U_{0j} = 0.047$, significance value <0.001. The correlation coefficient of this study group, ICC_1 represents degree of variation, and ICC_2 refers to the reliability of the mean of entire group. The ICC_1 is calculated as (between-group variation, of τ_{00}) / (total variation $\tau_{00} + \delta^2$). The $ICC_1 = \tau_{00} / (\tau_{00} + \delta^2) = 0.047 / (0.047 + 0.257) = 0.156$. ICC_1 of 0.156 refers that the between-group variation that cannot be ignored, which means that the competitive advantage of vocation school is significantly related to the reform project. Secondly, the $ICC_2 = 0.86$ is the reliability of the mean of the entire group.

4.2 Random Coefficient Regression Model

According to the previous analysis, both ICC_1 and ICC_2 show that competitive advantages among schools are significantly different. Random coefficient regression model is applied in this research to examine the relationship between the TVE reform project and school's competitive advantage. Below is the results of the model.

The fix effect is presented as the following: γ_{00} (intercept) = 0.547, with significant value <0.001, and γ_{10} (slope) = 0.844, with significant value <0.001. Both values are significant. Random effect is presented as the following: $r_{ij} = 0.065$, $u_{0j} = 0.193$, with significant value <0.001, $u_{1j} = 0.012$, with significant value <0.001. Both variables are significant.

4.3 Intercept-as-Outcome Model

The fix effects are the intercept $\gamma_{00} = 3.787$, with significant value <0.001, $\gamma_{01} = 0.988$, with significant value <0.001. and slope $\gamma_{10} = 0.844$, with significant value <0.001, $\gamma_{11} = 0.028$, with significant value > 0.001, which is not significant. The random effects are the variation numbers $r_{ij} = 0.255$, $u_{0j} = 0.091$, with significant value <0.001. $u_{1j} = 0.112$, with significant value > 0.001.

According to the above analysis, the strategies of the TVE reform project and the organizational culture have a significant and positive influences on the competitive advantage. However, the moderating effect of organizational culture is not significant.

4.4 Hypothesis Testing

According to the hypotheses propose in this study, the HLM has analyzed the variables which prove the establishment of hypotheses. Results are summarized as follows in the table below, and conclusions of the test results are shown in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis	Research Result
H ₁ : The strategies of the TVE reform project of individual-level have a significant positive influence on competitive advantage	Established
H ₂ : Organizational culture variables of organizational level have a significant positive influence on competitive advantage	Established
H ₃ : The moderating effect of organizational culture in the strategies of the TVE reform project on competitive advantage degree is not significant	Not Established

5 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The study constructs the relationship among strategies of Phase II of the TVE Reform Project, organizational culture and competitive advantage of TVE Institutions by hierarchical linear model. The positive influences between variables of strategies of Phase II of the TVE Reform Project and competitive advantage were supported. The positive influences between variables of organizational culture and competitive advantage were supported, too. However, the moderating effect of organizational culture were not supported. Finally, according to the results of empirical study, the suggestions for strategies of the technological and vocational education and future research were proposed.

Phase II of the TVE reform project has taken place from 2013 to 2017 in Taiwan. The project will conclude in the middle of this year. As the TVE reform project has successfully impact on technical and vocational schools, technical and vocational colleges and universities in Taiwan. The implementation of the project is able to shorten the gap between industry and education, and cultivates job-required expertise skills of students of TVE schools, and the government believes that this program should continue to promote. The characteristics of technical and vocational education are closely linked with the practice of industry and the cultivation of the practical needs into the industry. Curriculum flexibility, equipment updates, technical practices, and employment convergence should get a higher attention in order to effectively solve the industrial and school gaps and problems.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Ministry of Education, Taiwan, Phase II of the TVE Reform Project, (2013), http://depart.moe.edu.tw/ED2300/News_Content.aspx?n=5D06F8190A65710E&sms=0DB78B5F69DB38E4&s=017DEA1AAFE8DA9D
Website of Department of Technological and Vocational Education, MOE, Taiwan.
- [2] Lapiņa, I., Kairiša, I., & Aramina, D., (2015), Role of Organizational Culture in the Quality Management of University. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 770-774.
- [3] Arabaci, İ. B., (2013), School Management by Values According to Teachers'

Opinions. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 103, 801-806.
doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2013.10.401>.

- [4] Kathleen, C., (2003), Principals and student achievement: What the research says. *VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development*.
- [5] Prahalad, C. K. and Gary Hamel, (1990), "The core competence of the corporation," *Harvard Business Review*, Boston, Vol.68, Iss.3, pp. 79-91.
- [6] Mazzarol, T., & Soutar, G. N., (1999), Sustainable competitive advantage for educational institutions: A suggested model. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 13(6), 287-300. Retrieved from ProQuest Education Journals (229204492).
- [7] Lynch, R. & Baines, P., (2004), Strategy development in UK higher education : Towards resource-based competitive advantages. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 26(2), 171-187.